

Towards multi-modal Learning by Demonstration: Combining depthless visual data with kinesthetic teaching

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Abstract— Human-human learning is usually conducted utilizing multiple modalities (verbal, visual, kinesthetic etc), which is proven to significantly improve the quality of communication between the teacher and the learner. Towards extending this idea to human-robot learning, we propose here a multi-modal scheme for robot Learning by Demonstration (LbD), that combines visual observation of the human hand from a depthless RGB camera, with enhanced direct kinesthetic teaching of the robot. The proposed method, exploits the visually perceived action of the human hand, to provide haptic guidance during kinesthetic teaching, facilitating corrections along the axes with the maximum uncertainty. The method is experimentally evaluated using an RGB camera and a UR10e robot, and compared against single-modal approaches, i.e. visually trained behavior and trained through kinesthetic teaching. Our method is shown to outperform the latter, in terms of both the quality of skill transfer, and the cognitive/physical load required for the training.

I. INTRODUCTION

Future robots are expected to coexist, collaborate and progressively learn from humans, while alleviating their cognitive and physical burden. Therefore, a key requirement for such systems is the ability to acquire knowledge from humans to develop new skills. Unlike explicit robot programming, which demands technical programming skills, Learning by Demonstration (LbD), or “Programming by Demonstration”, is a notion recently introduced in robotics to provide robots with such capabilities [1], [2].

Learning by Demonstration is based on data from human demonstrations, which can be captured through multiple means. The most dominant methods for capturing such data in the literature either involve external sensors, e.g. cameras or wearable sensors, or employ the notion of “kinesthetic teaching”, according to which the robot is taught through direct physical guidance by the human. Although LbD through visual observation is more intuitive for the human-teacher, it suffers from high uncertainty, sourcing from the sensor characteristics, the detectability of the human hand, and

possible occlusions. On the other hand, data gathered through kinesthetic teaching do not usually involve uncertainty, but the process can be physically and cognitively demanding, due to the robot’s dynamics and the compliant control scheme employed for enabling the physical guidance.

Learning through visual observations of the human-teacher, e.g. visual data captured through a camera, is a well-studied topic in the literature [2]–[10]. Some works tackle the problem in a higher decision-making level [8], considering the prior knowledge of some action-motion primitives (e.g. pushing, pulling), others infer/reconstruct the motion from static RGB images [3], while others consider the problem of capturing and encoding the trajectory of the actual motion required for the task execution from video streams [6], [7], [9], [10]. In the latter category, which is the focus of this paper, some works employ Neural Networks [7], [9], which however require a large-size dataset, e.g. in [9] more than 10,000 videos were utilized to encode the skills, while others utilize a relatively small dataset (max 2-3 videos), e.g. by considering multiple demonstration-iterations while optimizing the view-angle of the observation [6] or by recreating the lost data based on known kinematic models [10]. However, it is commonly accepted in the literature, that data captured through RGB (or even RGB-D) sensors suffer from high uncertainty in the depth axis of the sensor, which heavily affects the quality of LbD.

Kinesthetic teaching enables direct skill transfer by allowing the human to physically guide the robot in demonstrating the motion. In contrast to visual observation, kinesthetic teaching does not involve any uncertainty, as proprioceptive sensors (e.g. joint encoders) of the robot are utilized for capturing the motion. However, since there is a physical human-robot interaction, compliant control schemes, such as impedance/admittance control or basic gravity compensation, are essential. These control strategies significantly impact the quality of captured data. To enhance this process, prior works have explored impedance and admittance control, leveraging partial task knowledge [11], iterative physical demonstrations [12], [13], and related concepts such as progressive automation [14] and incremental learning [15].

Human-centric environments are often unstructured, cluttered and heavily dynamic, which makes learning through only a single means difficult and some times impossible, in terms of skill transferability. Furthermore, learning among human beings rarely involves a single communication channel. On the contrary, human-human learning is multi-modal, e.g. verbal/linguistic, visual (through demonstration), kinesthetic (for basic skills) etc, which is shown to be beneficial

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for the learning process [16]. Some attempts to tackle the problem of multi-modal LbD in robotics literature involve high level robot programming through a composition of basic actions [17], the combination of cameras and wearable sensors [2], refinement of kinesthetic teaching through post-training visualizations [18] or combining kinesthetic with simulations [19]. To the best of the authors' knowledge, the exploitation of visual data from depthless cameras for enhancing the kinesthetic teaching of a task has not previously been studied, in the context of LbD.

In this work, we propose an LbD method that combines the advantages of both visual and kinesthetic teaching, offering the intuitiveness and effortlessness of learning through observation while benefiting from the accuracy of kinesthetic teaching. Our approach involves a two-stage scheme that leverages visual data from a single demonstration, captured by a depthless camera, to assist the human-teacher in kinesthetic task instruction. The proposed method assumes access to an algorithm for detecting the human-hand configuration from RGB images (without depth or camera distance information), and does not require knowledge of the camera's location relative to an inertial frame.

II. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION AND CONCEPT SOLUTION

Consider the availability of a visual observation of a manual "post-grasp" task performed by a human, i.e. a video of a human hand executing a specific task. A "post-grasp task" here refers to hand movements after grasping an object, such as detaching a fruit from a branch. Let us adopt the reasonable assumption that depth information is either altogether absent from the visual observation data (i.e. an RGB camera was utilized for the frame capture), or is characterized by a relatively high uncertainty. The position and the orientation of the camera with respect to the scene is not considered to be known a priori. Let $\mathbf{x} \triangleq [\mathbf{p}^\top \mathbf{Q}^\top]^\top \in \mathcal{T}$, be the actual generalized pose of the human hand, e.g. of the wrist, where $\mathbf{p}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and $\mathbf{Q}(t) \in \mathbb{S}^3$ are the position (in Cartesian coordinates form) and orientation (in unit quaternion form) of the hand respectively, with $\mathcal{T} \triangleq \mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{S}^3$ representing the generalized pose space of the hand and $\mathbb{S}^n \triangleq \{\mathbf{a} \in \mathbb{R}^{n+1} : \|\mathbf{a}\|=1\}$ the set of unit vectors (unit sphere). We further assume access to an algorithm that can estimate the human hand's position and orientation relative to the camera, e.g. MediaPipe Hands [20] or OpenPose [21]. Let $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_h(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and $\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_h(t) \in \mathbb{S}^3$ respectively denote the algorithm-estimated position (in pixel space) and orientation of the hand relative to the camera frame $\{C\}$ during the video, where $t \in [0, T]$, with $T \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ representing the demonstration duration. Figure 1 depicts the uncertainty involved in the estimated pose of the human hand.

Our aim is to exploit the initial available information captured by the camera, i.e. $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_h(t)$, $\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_h(t)$, by accounting for their anisotropic uncertainty, in order to encode the skill and subsequently transfer it to the robot. To this end, we propose the augmentation of the visually perceived motion through kinesthetic means, i.e. through physical human-robot interaction, during the autonomous execution of the task by

Fig. 1: Uncertainty involved in visual observation.

the robot. A novel aspect of our approach, introduced to ensure that this augmentation is user-intuitive as well as efficient, involves using the uncertainty of the visual data to render anisotropic compliance characteristics to the robot's admittance control, i.e. relatively large kinesthetic corrections are allowed only along the directions in which the uncertainty of the initially perceived motion is relatively high.

III. PROPOSED METHOD

A. LbD through visual observation

Consider an algorithm able of identifying the 21 anatomical key-points of the human hand, i.e. four for each finger and one at the wrist, as shown in the upper part of Fig. 2. We define the hand pose based on key-points \mathbf{p}_a , \mathbf{p}_b , \mathbf{p}_c , $\mathbf{p}_d \in \mathbb{R}^3$, with \mathbf{p}_a , \mathbf{p}_c , \mathbf{p}_d representing the three vertices of the palm triangle, and \mathbf{p}_b being the base of the thumb, as depicted in Fig. 2. Notice that all three coordinates of those points are considered to be estimated (as they belong to \mathbb{R}^3), which is commonly the case for detection algorithms such as the MediaPipe algorithm; however, the z -coordinate of \mathbf{p}_a (wrist) is always zero, as it is the base key-point and therefore it is considered by definition to lie on the camera projection plane. The estimated position of the human hand is considered to be represented by the wrist and therefore $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_h \triangleq \mathbf{p}_a$, while the estimated orientation of the human hand in a rotation matrix form is defined as:

$$\hat{\mathbf{R}}_h \triangleq [\mathbf{x}_h \ \mathbf{y}_h \ \mathbf{z}_h] \in SO(3), \quad (1)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{z}_h &\triangleq \frac{\mathbf{p}_{ab} + \mathbf{p}_{ap}}{\|\mathbf{p}_{ab} + \mathbf{p}_{ap}\|} \in \mathbb{S}^2, \\ \mathbf{x}_h &\triangleq \frac{(\mathbf{I}_3 - \mathbf{z}_h \mathbf{z}_h^\top) \mathbf{p}_{ab}}{\|(\mathbf{I}_3 - \mathbf{z}_h \mathbf{z}_h^\top) \mathbf{p}_{ab}\|} \in \mathbb{S}^2, \\ \mathbf{y}_h &\triangleq \mathbf{z}_h \times \mathbf{x}_h \in \mathbb{S}^2, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

with $\mathbf{p}_{ai} \triangleq \mathbf{p}_i - \mathbf{p}_a$, $\forall i \in \{b, c, d\}$, $\mathbf{p}_{ap} \triangleq \frac{\mathbf{p}_{ac} + \mathbf{p}_{ad}}{2}$, $\mathbf{I}_3 \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$ the identity matrix and " \times " denoting the cross product. The calculation of the corresponding unit quaternion representation $\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_h$ from $\hat{\mathbf{R}}_h$ is straightforward. The z -axis is defined to point toward the opening between the palm and thumb, the primary prehensile component of the human hand.

Further, notice the similarity of the direction of the z -axis of the human hand, with that of the robotic gripper (bottom image of Fig. 2), which facilitates motion mapping for human-to-robot skill transferability.

Fig. 2: Visual detection of the pose of the human hand and the frames of the hand and robotic gripper considered.

Based on the recorded observation during a complete demonstration, i.e. $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_h(t), \hat{\mathbf{Q}}_h(t), t \in [0, T]$, we employ the Dynamic Movement Primitives (DMP) model [22] to encode the spatial and temporal characteristics of the motion. This particular choice has the benefit of single-shot model training. For the orientation part, the method proposed in [23] is utilized, which takes advantage of logarithmic mapping. The DMP model in the task-space, involves the motion generation through the on-line solution of a dynamical system, which can be expressed as follows:

$$\tau \dot{\mathbf{x}}_d = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_d; \mathbf{W}), \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_d \triangleq [\mathbf{p}_d^T \mathbf{Q}_d^T \dot{\mathbf{p}}_d^T \boldsymbol{\omega}_d^T z]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{14}$ is the state of the model (motion generation mechanism), with $\mathbf{p}_d \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $\mathbf{Q}_d \in \mathbb{S}^3$ being the generated reference position and unit quaternion respectively, $\boldsymbol{\omega}_d \in \mathbb{R}^3$ the generated angular velocity reference, and $z \in \mathbb{R}$ the so-called phase variable that serves as a replacement of time (one can refer to [22] for more details). Moreover, $\mathbf{f}(\cdot) : \mathbb{R}^{14} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{14}$ is the nonlinear function that maps the states to their derivatives, $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times N}$ the tunable parameters that essentially encode the motion, with $N \in \mathbb{N}$ being their number, while $\tau \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ is the time scaling parameter, through which the speed and duration of motion can be adjusted; $\tau > 1$ induces a motion with lower speed than the one demonstrated, while $\tau < 1$ induces a faster motion. Given the demonstrated motion, there are many different options to compute the \mathbf{W} values so that the generated motion (i.e. the evolution of the dynamical system) optimally mimics the demonstrated data set. The most common methods for calculating the optimal parameters \mathbf{W} are the Least Squares and the Locally Weighted Regression [22].

Remark 1. We emphasize that the estimated position and orientation of the human hand is recorded with respect to the initial identified frame of the human hand, $\{U\}$, detected by the camera at $t = 0$. Hence, the entire motion is encoded with respect to the initial grasp pose of the hand. Furthermore, given that the motion is encoded without accounting for depth information, the units of $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_h$ are not specific, but they are actually on the pixel space of the camera. However, due to the inherent spatial scaling properties of DMPs, simply defining the initial and target pose aptly adjusts the motion to be executed to the task needs, thereby compensating for this unit inconsistency of the training dataset.

B. Kinesthetic corrections

Following the initial stage, where a DMP is trained using visual data (as detailed in Subsection III-A), we propose a second stage in which the robot autonomously executes the motion with the ability, however, to introduce compliance when deemed necessary by the human user to allow for kinesthetic corrections. To further assist the user and reduce cognitive and physical effort, the compliance is enhanced along the axis with the highest current model uncertainty, as estimated based on the uncertainty in the camera's viewpoint during the visual demonstration.

To provide the system with compliant characteristics, we employ the notion of admittance control. Therefore, a target impedance model in the task-space of the robot is defined for the robot's end-effector, as follows:

$$\mathbf{M} \dot{\boldsymbol{\delta}}_v + \mathbf{D} \boldsymbol{\delta}_v + \mathbf{K} \mathbf{e} = \mathbf{F}_x, \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{M}, \mathbf{D}, \mathbf{K} \in S_{++}^6$ are the target 6D task-space positive definite inertia, damping and stiffness matrices respectively, $\boldsymbol{\delta}_v \in \mathbb{R}^6$ represents the desired deviation from the reference velocity induced by the admittance model, while $\mathbf{F}_x \triangleq [\mathbf{f}^T \boldsymbol{\tau}^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^6$ is the generalized force measurement at the end-effector with $\mathbf{f}, \boldsymbol{\tau} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ being the force and torque applied by the user to the end-effector, with S_{++}^n denoting the set of positive definite matrices. Moreover,

$$\mathbf{e} \triangleq [(\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_d)^T \log(\mathbf{Q} * \mathbf{Q}_d^{-1})^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^6, \quad (5)$$

is the error between the robot's pose, denoted with $\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $\mathbf{Q} \in \mathbb{S}^3$, and the reference pose generated by the visually trained DMP. Here, $\log(\cdot) : \mathbb{S}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$ is the quaternion logarithmic mapping, “*” represents the quaternion product, and $\mathbf{Q}_d^{-1} \in \mathbb{S}^3$ the quaternion inverse of \mathbf{Q}_d (more details on quaternion algebra can be found in [24]).

For rendering these specific compliant characteristics, the commanded joint velocities are computed by:

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}} = \mathbf{J}^\dagger \left(\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\mathbf{p}}_d \\ \boldsymbol{\omega}_d \end{bmatrix} + \boldsymbol{\delta}_v \right), \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{R}^m$ are the joint variables and $\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{q}) \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times m}$ the Jacobian matrix of the robot, with m being the number of joints and “ \dagger ” symbolizing any pseudo inverse matrix, e.g. the inverse if $m = 6$.

Based on (4), the selection of the impedance model parameters plays a crucial role on the directions in which the user

is guided during the interaction with the robot. Specifically, the reactive force experienced by the user along a specific direction is proportional to the values of the corresponding elements of matrices \mathbf{M} , \mathbf{D} and \mathbf{K} . Our aim is to append low impedance along the directions with high uncertainty.

As described in Section II, the estimated hand pose by the camera includes a measurement error, which is considered to be a random variable having a normal distribution: $\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}_6, \mathbf{\Sigma})$, with $\mathbf{\Sigma} \in S_{++}^6$ being the variance-covariance matrix of its uncertainty. Notice that, as mentioned in Remark 1, the measurement error is defined with respect to the initial pose of the human hand, as detected by the camera, i.e. with respect to $\{U\}$. In practical applications, as $\mathbf{\Sigma}$ is generally unknown, one can use an estimate of the uncertainty. More specifically, given the the initial robot’s end-effector pose at the start of the kinesthetic correction phase, denoted as $\mathbf{R}_0 \in SO(3)$, the uncertainty with respect to the robot’s base frame is calculated as follows:

$$\mathbf{\Sigma} \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{\Sigma}_p & \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} \\ \mathbf{0}_{3 \times 3} & \mathbf{\Sigma}_o \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{\Sigma}_c \mathbf{A}^\top, \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{A} \triangleq \mathbf{R}_0 \mathbf{R}_{cu}^\top \otimes \mathbf{I}_2 \in \mathbb{R}^6$ with $\mathbf{R}_{cu} \in SO(3)$ being the rotation matrix of frame $\{U\}$ (initially identified pose of the human hand) with respect to the camera frame and “ \otimes ” representing the Kronecker product, while $\mathbf{\Sigma}_c \in S_{++}^6$ represents the block-diagonal (for decoupled position and orientation) uncertainty of the camera with respect to its own frame. In such a case, for an RGB camera (or for a low-depth-resolution RGB-D camera), we could consider $\mathbf{\Sigma}_c = \text{diag}(\underline{\sigma}, \underline{\sigma}, \bar{\sigma}, \underline{\varsigma}, \bar{\varsigma}, \underline{\varsigma})^2$ with $\underline{\sigma}, \bar{\sigma}, \underline{\varsigma}, \bar{\varsigma} \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ and $\underline{\sigma} \ll \bar{\sigma}, \underline{\varsigma} \ll \bar{\varsigma}$, as the estimation involves low uncertainty only along the pixel space direction (x, y of the camera) and the rotation around its z -axis. Notice that the units of $\underline{\sigma}, \bar{\sigma}$ are “meters” and those of $\underline{\varsigma}, \bar{\varsigma}$ are “radians”. Hence, the expected deviations can be estimated on the basis of rough estimates for the motion’s range.

Under the aforementioned rationale, and given the uncertainty involved in the DMP model after the initial stage (i.e. visual training), we propose the utilization of the following anisotropic stiffness matrix:

$$\mathbf{K} \triangleq \text{diag} \left(\frac{k_p}{\lambda_{pM}} \mathbf{I}_3, \frac{k_o}{\lambda_{oM}} \mathbf{I}_3 \right) \mathbf{\Sigma}^{-1}, \quad (8)$$

where $\lambda_{pM}, \lambda_{oM} \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ respectively denote the maximum eigenvalues of $\mathbf{\Sigma}_p^{-1}, \mathbf{\Sigma}_o^{-1}$, while $k_p, k_o \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ represent the selected stiffness value on the major axis of \mathbf{K} for position and orientation, respectively.

At the end of the kinesthetic correction stage, the recorded refined motion of the end-effector, i.e. $\mathbf{p}(t), \mathbf{Q}(t), \forall t \in [0, T]$, is used to retrain the DMP model.

Remark 2. *The learning process could possibly include additional kinesthetic correction iterations, which are expected to enhance the task learning.*

The overall multi-modal training scheme has been implemented in Python, utilizing the MediaPipe algorithm [20],

and is publicly available¹.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

The proposed scheme of multi-modal LbD was experimentally evaluated considering the scenario shown in Fig. 3. The task involves moving a tool along a circular path (approximately 1.5 turns) around an axis, to which the tool is connected via a thread. The task duration is $T \approx 10.5$ s. A plain RGB webcam (*Creative Live! Cam*) is used to capture data for visual training, in 30 fps. The image captured by the camera is shown in Fig. 4. Note that, given the viewpoint of the camera, the motion trajectory is ellipsoidal when projected to the camera’s visual plane.

The robotic agent is a *Universal Robots UR10e* manipulator, equipped with a custom gripper, as shown in the bottom image of Fig. 2. The gripper features three 3d-printed fingers made from a flexible material (thermoplastic polyurethane, TPU), which are actuated by a single motor. This design enables safe and adaptive grasping of various objects, as the flexible fingers conform to the shape of the object being grasped. In addition, a custom dual-handle attachment, mounted between the robot’s tool flange and the gripper, facilitates hand guidance of the robot during kinesthetic training. This is employed either for a) single-modal training using the robot’s in-built “teach mode” function, or b) the correction stage of the proposed multi-modal scheme, implemented through the anisotropic admittance controller (4). For the latter, a pushbutton, integrated in one of the handles, is used to allow user intervention by engaging the kinesthetic correction mode during execution of the visually learned motion. The force measurement required in (4) is provided by the in-build 6d force/torque sensor of UR10e, after compensating for the gripper’s gravity and applying a dead-zone filter of 4 N for the force and 0.5 Nm for torque.

The parameters of the multi-modal training scheme were specified as $\mathbf{M} = \text{diag}(10\mathbf{I}_3, 0.1\mathbf{I}_3)$, $\mathbf{D} = \text{diag}(40\mathbf{I}_3, 1.5\mathbf{I}_3)$, $k_p = 200$ N/m, $k_o = 80$ Nm/rad, $\underline{\sigma} = 10^{-3}$ m, $\bar{\sigma} = 10^3$ m, $\underline{\varsigma} = \pi/20$ rad, $\bar{\varsigma} = \pi$ rad. The DMP model uses 20 kernels. We note that the minor axis of \mathbf{K}_p is towards the y -axis with an eigenvalue that approaches zero, which means that corrections are freely facilitated along the y -axis in translation. For \mathbf{K}_o , the minor axis is towards the $x-z$ plane, with corresponding eigenvalues equal to 0.2 Nm/rad (as opposed to 80 Nm/rad exhibited along the other axis), facilitating corrections towards these directions for orientation.

For evaluating the proposed method, we compare it against a) skill learning based solely on the initial visual data, and b) skill learning through direct kinesthetic teaching (henceforth referred to as “kinesthetic-only”), using the “teach mode” of UR10e. In all cases, the robot starts from the same initial configuration to ensure a fair comparison.

The initial configuration during physical interaction of the human with the robot is shown in Fig. 5a. The paths of the robot’s tip followed during the proposed kinesthetic corrections method (blue line) and during single-modal

¹<https://github.com/CSRL-HMU/Multimodal-Visual-Kinesthetic-LbD>

Fig. 3: The post-grasp task considered for the experimental evaluation of the proposed method.

kinesthetic-only teaching (red line) are shown in Fig. 6a, alongside with the visually trained model (black line). It can be observed that due to the lack of depth information in the RGB video, the visually trained motion remains essentially planar and takes on an ellipsoidal shape. The trajectory of the kinesthetic-only training exhibits considerable oscillations, resulting from the fact that the human experiences the dynamics of the system. It should also be noted that, in this case, the user was unable to complete the demonstration within the nominal task duration of 10.5 s, with the motion ending approximately a quarter-circle early. This reflects the high cognitive load imposed on the user while attempting to compensate for the robot’s dynamics.

The initial configuration of the robot during the autonomous task execution, after the DMP encoding of the training data, is shown in Fig. 5b. Figure 6b depicts the paths followed by the tip of the robot during execution of the task. In this case, the DMP-generated reference tip trajectory ($\mathbf{p}_d, \dot{\mathbf{p}}_d, \ddot{\mathbf{p}}_d$) is tracked using the Closed Loop Inverse Kinematics (CLIK) algorithm, without accounting for the external forces exerted on the tool. Notice, in Fig. 6b, the absence of erroneous oscillations in the kinesthetic-only case, due to the filtering induced by the Gaussian function approximation of the DMP. Here, in order to assess the task performance, we estimate the radius of curvature of the path, denoted with $\hat{r}(t) \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$, in each case, at 100 equally distributed time instances within the duration of each motion², based on the following formula [25]:

$$\hat{r}(t) = \frac{\|\dot{\mathbf{p}}_d\|^3}{\sqrt{\|\dot{\mathbf{p}}_d\|^2 \|\ddot{\mathbf{p}}_d\|^2 - (\dot{\mathbf{p}}_d^\top \ddot{\mathbf{p}}_d)^2}},$$

and we compare it with the reference radius (i.e. the thread’s length), which is $r \approx 0.225$ m. The box-plots in Fig. 7 show the statistical distributions of the thus estimated radius of curvature for each case. It can be seen that the proposed method yields a learned motion that is notably closer to the reference task —at least in terms of this specific performance metric— compared to the single-modal approaches. Due to its ellipsoidal shape, the visually trained motion exhibits relatively high curvature. In contrast, the curvature of the motion trained through kinesthetic-only teaching is evidently lower than the reference, as the aforementioned

²Radius of curvature cannot be estimated when the robot is static, due to $\dot{\mathbf{p}}_d, \ddot{\mathbf{p}}_d$ being close to zero.

DMP-induced filtering is insufficient to fully correct the motion.

Fig. 4: Snapshots of the visual teaching stage, acquired by the webcam during the task demonstration.

Fig. 5: Kinesthetic training stage and autonomous task execution.

To compare the methods in terms of physical effort requirements, we consider the energy transferred from human to robot during hand guidance, computed using:

$$E^+ = \int_0^T \max(0, \mathbf{v}^\top \mathbf{F}) dt.$$

For the kinesthetic-only approach (without prior visual information) the transferred energy is computed as 35.01 J, whereas the kinesthetic correction stage of the multi-modal scheme requires only 4.92 J. This seven-fold improvement highlights the considerable efficiency advantage of the proposed method.

Fig. 6: Path followed by the robot's tip during (a) training, and (b) execution of the learned task. Black dashed line depicts a circle of radius equal to the thread's length (0.225 m), while the solid small linear segments indicate the tool z-axis at regular time intervals. The initial and final positions are denoted with "x" and "o" markers respectively (all initial positions coincide).

Fig. 7: Statistics of the learned path's radius of curvature in each case.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a novel method for a two-stage LbD is introduced, that combines depthless visual data with kinesthetic teaching for efficient human-to-robot skill transfer. In the core of the proposed admittance-based method lies an anisotropic stiffness matrix, which is defined based on the uncertainty of the visually perceived motion, to facilitate the human-teacher along the axis in which the system is currently less confident. The method is shown to outperform the single-modal learning, namely the training through solely visual or kinesthetic means, in terms of both skill transferability and physical load requirements. The tests consider a task involving a rhythmic circular motion around an axis.

Future work will involve detailed studies for the specification of the anisotropic stiffness parameters, as well as different use cases (e.g. fruit hand-picking or pick-and-place tasks). In addition, possible extensions to the proposed method will be explored, e.g. taking into account the uncertainty of the hand keypoints' detection algorithm, considering multiple kinesthetic correction iterations, or multi-view visual demonstrations.

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